

DECISION MAKING BEHAVIORS AND PRACTICES OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL HEADS IN AREA II DIVISION OF BATANGAS

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to assess the decision-making behaviors and practices of public elementary school heads in Area II, Division of Batangas with the end view of developing a management program on decision making behaviors and practices as an output of the study. The descriptive method of research was utilized in the study with the aid of a questionnaire as the main data gathering instrument complemented by an interview. The respondents were 115 school heads and 298 teachers in the province of Batangas. The statistical tools utilized were weighted mean, t-test and F-test. Based on the results of the study, majority of the respondents belonged to ages 41 to 50 years, female, married, occupying the Head teacher position, master's degree holders, and had attended four to seven seminars. Elementary school heads strongly agreed on the different parameters of decision-making behaviors in terms of cognitive, affective and action-oriented aspects. School heads strongly agreed on decision making practices in terms of academic and supervisory functions. There is no significant difference on the decision-making behaviors of the respondents when grouped according to age, civil status, and educational attainment. There was a significant difference in their decision-making behaviors when grouped according to sex and position. The management program was designed based on the least rated competencies on decision making behaviors and practices of the respondents.

Keywords: Management; decision making behaviors, decision making practices, school heads